

Exploring Elitism Strategies in Nested Tournament Selection for Multi-Objective Genetic Programming

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Abstract

Nested Tournament (NT) is a multi-objective (MO) selection method that potentially enables fine-grained control of selection pressure by evaluating objectives sequentially within a hierarchical tournament structure. Although NT has already been employed in Genetic Programming (GP), the interaction between NT and elitism, a core element of Evolutionary Algorithms, remains largely unexplored. This article presents a systematic empirical investigation of elitism strategies within the NT framework for GP, with particular emphasis on integrating NSGA-II into NT selection. We evaluate several elitism mechanisms: NT with the NSGA-II population replacement, elitism based on crowding-distance and first-objective, and a novel ideal-point elitism, and compare them against NT without elitism and the standard NSGA-II. Experiments are conducted using two, three, and five objectives for the accuracy-complexity trade-off. Results show that elitism design critically influences the stability, efficiency, and diversity preservation of NT-based search. While NSGA-II elitism provides a principled and transferable mechanism within NT, simpler NT elitism strategies achieve comparable performance at lower computational cost. Moreover, NSGA-II strategies were less effective at preserving semantic diversity. Overall, the findings highlight NT as an efficient MO alternative to selection methods based on Pareto Fronts.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Genetic programming**.

Keywords

genetic programming, multi-objective optimization, nested tournament selection, NSGA-II, elitism

1 Introduction

Many real-world learning and modeling tasks are inherently Multi-Objective (MO), requiring the simultaneous optimization of conflicting criteria such as predictive accuracy, model complexity, interpretability, and generalization. In Genetic Programming (GP) [8], this MO nature is particularly evident in symbolic regression, where

highly accurate solutions often come at the cost of excessive structural complexity, reduced interpretability, and increased susceptibility to overfitting [2]. As a result, Multi-Objective Optimization (MOO) has become a central paradigm for GP-based learning, motivating the development of selection mechanisms capable of navigating complex trade-offs among competing objectives. The dominant approach to MOO in evolutionary computation relies on Pareto-front (PF)-based selection methods, with NSGA-II [4] standing out as one of the most widely adopted and influential algorithms. By combining non-dominated sorting, crowding-distance-based diversity preservation, and elitist population replacement, NSGA-II has demonstrated strong empirical performance across a broad range of domains. However, its effectiveness is known to degrade as the number of objectives increases [5], a setting that is increasingly relevant in modern GP applications where multiple complexity and interpretability measures are optimized simultaneously. In such many-objective scenarios, dominance relations weaken, selection pressure diminishes, and the computational cost of PF construction and diversity estimation becomes substantial. An alternative and comparatively underexplored class of MO selection mechanisms is based on sequential or hierarchical evaluation of objectives rather than explicit Pareto dominance. Nested Tournament (NT) selection [1, 9, 19] belongs to this family. NT extends standard tournament selection by evaluating objectives sequentially within a nested structure, enabling multiple criteria to influence selection without requiring global dominance ranking or PF construction. A distinctive advantage of NT is its explicit control over selection pressure across objectives through tournament-size parametrization, offering flexibility that is largely absent in traditional PF-based approaches. Despite these appealing properties and sporadic use in the GP literature, often under different names [1, 6, 9, 19], NT has not been systematically studied as a general-purpose MOO selection mechanism.

One fundamental aspect that remains largely unresolved in NT-based evolutionary algorithms is the design of effective elitism strategies. Elitism plays a critical role in preserving high-quality solutions [15], stabilizing evolutionary dynamics, and ensuring convergence toward competitive trade-offs. While elitism is deeply integrated and well understood in PF-based algorithms such as

NSGA-II, NT selection does not naturally prescribe a canonical elitist mechanism. Existing applications either employ ad-hoc elitism rules, rely on purely generational replacement, or implicitly inherit elitism from unrelated selection components. As a consequence, the interaction between NT selection and elitism, particularly in GP and many-objective settings, remains poorly understood.

This work addresses this gap by presenting a systematic empirical investigation of elitism strategies within the NT framework for MOGP. Specifically, we study how different elitism mechanisms influence predictive performance, structural complexity, fitness diversity preservation, and computational efficiency. We consider both principled PF-based elitism, obtained by integrating NSGA-II population replacement into NT selection, and simpler objective-driven elitism schemes, including first-objective, crowding-distance-based, and ideal-point elitism. These approaches are compared against NT without elitism and against standard NSGA-II, allowing a comprehensive assessment of trade-offs between algorithmic complexity and empirical performance.

The manuscript is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces some of the fundamental concepts on which this work is based, including multi-objective optimization in GP, NSGA-II and NT. Section 3 describes the employed test cases and experimental settings. Section 4 presents and discusses the obtained results. Finally, Section 5 concludes the work and proposes ideas for future research.

2 Background

2.1 Multi-objective Optimization in Genetic Programming

GP was originally introduced in the context of single-objective optimization, in which the evolutionary search is guided by a single fitness measure representing solution quality. In practice, however, MOO is a fundamental aspect to many GP applications, particularly in symbolic regression, where predictive performance must be balanced with structural complexity, interpretability, and generalization. Unlike scalarization-based approaches, commonly adopted in other machine learning paradigms (e.g., [3]), evolutionary algorithms, and GP in particular, are well suited for multiple, and potentially conflicting, objectives. This capability stems from their derivative-free search, which does not impose any assumption on the mathematical properties of the objective functions. Candidate solutions are instead evolved by genetic variation operators applied directly to their structure, enabling the simultaneous and probabilistic exploration of multiple trade-off solutions [7]. The following subsections review the main principles of NSGA-II and NT selection, which constitute the core MOGP approaches considered in this study.

2.2 NSGA-II

NSGA-II introduced three foundational components that have rapidly become standard in evolutionary MOO: (i) a fast non-dominated sorting procedure to reduce the high computational cost associated with PF-based sorting; (ii) an explicit elitist strategy for MOO; (iii) and a parameter-free diversity preservation mechanism based on crowding distance [4]. The algorithm operates under a $(\mu + \lambda)$ elitist framework, in which the parent population (P_t) and the full offspring population (Q_t), both containing N individuals,

are merged into a combined population of size $2N$. This population is then sorted into successive non-dominated fronts ($\mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2, \dots$). Elitism is enforced by deterministically filling the next generation with individuals from successive PFs until the population size N is reached. When inclusion of an entire PF would exceed N , individuals with the highest crowding distance from the this PF are selected. Crowding distance estimates the local density of solutions by measuring the perimeter of the largest cuboid in the objective space surrounding each individual without enclosing other points. This mechanism maintains diversity without requiring the manual specification of a sharing parameter, which was a significant limitation in previous methods [4]. By prioritizing solutions located in less crowded regions, the algorithm guides the search towards a diverse set of trade-offs among the optimization objectives [22].

Despite its widespread adoption, NSGA-II exhibits well-known limitations as the number of objectives increases beyond three [11]. In many-objective optimization problems, the proportion of non-dominated individuals in the population becomes exponentially large, leading to a severe reduction in selection pressure as most solutions collapse in the first PF [11]. Furthermore, the computational cost of calculating the crowding distance increases with dimensionality, while its effectiveness as a diversity estimator diminishes [11].

2.3 Nested Tournament Selection Method

NT selection is a MO selection method defined by a sequence of tournament selection operations, each associated with a distinct optimization objective. Rather than relying on global dominance relations, NT enforces objective-wise selection pressure through a hierarchical and sequential evaluation process. Figure 1 represents an example of the NT selection method. Selection begins at the first tournament level by randomly sampling individuals from the population with replacement, preserving the stochastic nature of standard tournament selection. Subsequent tournament levels are formed deterministically using only the winners of the preceding stage. As a consequence, individuals evaluated at deeper levels of the tournament are, on average, high-performing with respect to all previously considered objectives. This layered structure enables NT to maintain consistent selection pressure across multiple objectives, addressing a known limitation of PF-based selection methods, in which selection pressure may deteriorate in many-objective scenarios [22]. While PF-based approaches aim to approximate the full trade-off surface, NT allows the search to be biased toward specific regions of the PF through explicit, objective-specific control of selection pressure. Increasing pressure on a given objective concentrates selection toward regions optimizing that criterion, whereas lower pressure promotes broader exploration. As a result, NT often emphasizes central trade-offs in the PF, while retaining a probabilistic search behavior.

Despite its conceptual simplicity, NT selection has appeared only sporadically in the GP literature and under different nomenclatures. Early formulations of sequential tournament selection were introduced independently by Brameier and Banzhaf [1] and Luke and Panait [9, 10]. In Linear GP, Brameier and Banzhaf proposed a two-level tournament for fitness and diversity optimization, while Luke and Panait formalized the "double tournament" as a bloat-control mechanism by optimizing fitness and model size. The framework

Figure 1: Nested Tournament selection method. In this example, three selection criteria are used, respectively with tournament sizes 3, 2, and 3. The first tournament is formed by random sampling with replacement from the population.

was later extended to MO settings. Vanneschi et al. [19, 20] employed NT selection with five and six objectives in Geometric Semantic GP, and Vanneschi and Castelli [18] used NT to optimize RMSE and input-output correlation for soft target regularization. Rebuli et al. [2] studied NT with multiple levels for interpretable GP models. Other recent works have reused the Luke and Panait "double tournament" selection to study error and correlation optimization in grammar-based GP [14], and to control tree growth within GP-driven Branch-and-Bound search [12]. In this work, we adopt the term Nested Tournament, as it provides the most general characterization of this family of methods.

Although NT allows explicit control of selection pressure at each tournament level, a detailed analysis of these parameters is beyond the scope of this study. Instead, we focus on how different elitism mechanisms interact with NT selection to control solution complexity.

2.3.1 Nested Tournament Elitism. Many applications of NT selection in GP did not explicitly formalize elitist preservation strategies [1, 9, 10, 12, 14, 20]. Vanneschi et al. [18, 19] adopted a single-objective elitist strategy based on predictive performance, while Rebuli et al. [2] introduced an ideal candidate elitism approach. In the latter, elitism is defined with respect to a virtual reference point in the objective space, constructed from the best values observed for each objective during the evolutionary process. The elite individual is selected as the solution closest to this ideal point, using a preselected metric, allowing elitism to reflect MO trade-offs without relying on Pareto dominance.

These prior works highlight that elitism is not an inherent component of NT selection but a design choice that can influence evolutionary dynamics, particularly in MO and complexity-constrained settings. Despite this, a systematic analysis of how different elitism

strategies interact with NT selection remains largely unexplored. This gap motivates the investigation conducted in the present study.

3 Experimental Settings

The experiments were conducted using the SLIM_GSGP library [17], an open-source Python framework for GP. We extended the framework to support Multi-Objective Genetic Programming (MOGP), along with the implementation of traditional NSGA-II and NT selection. The updated library is publicly available at [<link removed to keep anonymity>](#).

3.1 Algorithms and Elitism Strategies

To examine the impact of elitism within the NT selection framework, this study evaluates a set of elitism strategies reflecting different principles of elite preservation in GP. These strategies range from PF-based elitism to objective-driven and non-elitist replacement schemes, allowing a systematic analysis of their effects on search dynamics, solution quality, model complexity, and diversity preservation. For benchmarking purposes, the standard NSGA-II algorithm, which does not rely on NT selection, is also included. The elitism mechanisms evaluated in this study are summarized as follows:

- **NSGA-II:** Standard NSGA-II algorithm using PF sorting and crowding-distance-based population replacement.
- **NT_NSQA-II:** NT selection is combined with NSGA-II population replacement. NT is used for parent selection to generate offspring, which are merged with the current population to form a $2N$ pool. From this pool, the next generation is obtained by selecting the best N individuals according to the PFs and crowding distance.
- **NT_CD:** NT selection with crowding-distance elitism, preserving the individual with the highest crowding distance among those in the first PF.
- **NT_1st_Obj:** NT selection with single-objective elitism, preserving the individual with the best value for the primary objective (RMSE).
- **NT_Ideal_Cand:** NT selection preserving the individual closest to an ideal point in the objective space, defined as a virtual point composed of the best values observed for each objective during the evolutionary process. This point is dynamically updated during the evolution, as long as better individuals for the different criteria are generated, leading to a dynamic management of elitism.
- **NT_NE:** NT selection without elitism, employing a purely generational replacement strategy.

3.2 Datasets

We selected three well-established symbolic regression benchmarks: Boston Housing (BH), Cooling Load (CL), and Toxicity (LD50), representing a range of structural challenges in terms of instance-to-feature ratios and predictive complexity. BH consists of 506 instances and 13 features and targets the median value of owner-occupied homes. CL comprises 768 instances and 8 features derived from simulated building geometries, with the goal of predicting cooling load. LD50 is a biological regression task with 234 samples

and 626 molecular descriptors, aimed at predicting the lethal dose to 50% of test subjects.

3.3 Statistical analysis

We used Monte Carlo cross-validation [21] with 30 independent 70/30 training/test splits, common to all algorithms. Statistical differences were evaluated using the Friedman test ($\alpha = 0.05$), followed by Nemenyi post-hoc tests ($\alpha = 0.05$) when significance was detected [16].

3.4 GP Configuration

Table 1 summarizes the GP hyperparameter configuration adopted in this study.

Table 1: GP settings used in all experiments.

Hyperparameter	Value
Population size	400
Number of generations	250
Initialization	ramped half-and-half [8]
Tree max initial depth	4
Tree max depth	17
Crossover probability (p_{xo})	0.8
Mutation probability (p_m)	0.2

The hyperparameter values were set to standard SLIM_GSGP defaults and the setup reported in Rebuli *et al.* [2]. To ensure comparability with the reference study, the total computational budget was fixed at 100,000 fitness evaluations. However, the population-generations trade-off was adjusted to emphasize larger population sizes, resulting in a population of 400 individuals evolved over 250 generations. This configuration was adopted to promote broader population-level diversity, which can be particularly relevant when assessing the interaction between selection and elitism mechanisms. The function set comprised standard arithmetic operators (+, −, ×, /) with protected division returning 1.0 when the absolute value of the denominator is $\leq 10^{-3}$, alongside protected non-arithmetic operators. Specifically, the modulo operator (%) returns zero when the denominator is zero, and the power operator returns the absolute value of the base when the base is negative and the exponent is fractional. For parent selection, the NSGA-II baseline employs a standard tournament size 2 based on the crowded-comparison operator. For all NT variants, a tournament size of 2 was consistently applied at each objective level. Although the ordering of objectives and the respective tournament sizes can influence selection pressure, these parameters were held constant in the present study to isolate the effects of elitism.

3.5 Optimization Objectives and Scenarios

The optimization objectives were selected to jointly capture predictive performance and structural complexity, following established practices in interpretable GP. Specifically, we considered one error-related objective and a set of complementary complexity measures that characterise both structural size and functional non-linearity:

- (1) **RMSE:** Root Mean Squared Error, defined as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}.$$
- (2) **Tree size:** Number of nodes in the tree.
- (3) **Features:** Count of unique Features in the tree.
- (4) **NAO:** Count of Non-Arithmetic Operators in the tree.
- (5) **NAOC:** Count of Consecutive Non-Arithmetic Operators in the tree.

To analyse the studied methods behavior under increasing objective dimensionality, three MO scenarios were defined. While all additional objectives aim to promote interpretability, their incremental inclusion reflects a deliberate progression from coarse structural control to a finer decomposition of model complexity. This design enables a controlled stress test of the selection mechanisms, particularly in relation to the well-documented limitations of PF-based algorithms in many-objective settings.

- **2 Objectives: [RMSE, Size].** This configuration represents the classic error vs. parsimony trade-off in GP, balancing predictive performance against overall model size.

- **3 Objectives: [RMSE, Size, Features].** This scenario extends the 2-objective scenario by incorporating the number of unique features as an additional objective. Conceptually, unique features count provides an additional dimension of model parsimony, directly linked to structural simplicity and interpretability [13].

- **5 Objectives: [RMSE, Size, Features, NAO, NAOC].** This scenario extends the 3-objective setting by incorporating functional non-linearity metrics. It also serves as a many-objective stress test, as PF-based methods such as NSGA-II are known to degrade beyond three objectives due to the rapid growth of non-dominated solutions and the consequent loss of selection pressure.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Computational Time

Although computational efficiency is not the main focus of this work, it is addressed first because it is largely independent of the datasets and objective configurations, offering a general view of the studied algorithms. Table 2 summarizes the mean and standard deviation of the computational times across the 30 independent runs for all datasets and objective scenarios. As the experiments were executed on shared computing resources without strict control over machine usage, their relative ranking across methods provides a more reliable basis for comparison than their absolute values.

Regardless of the dataset or the number of optimization objectives, the results indicate a consistent hierarchy of computational efficiency, which can be categorized into three distinct performance tiers. (i) NT_NE, NT_1st_Obj, NT_Ideal_Cand exhibit the lowest execution times. Within this group, NT_NE and NT_1st_Obj frequently alternate as the fastest variants. NT_Ideal_Cand usually follows as a close third, utilizing efficient matrix operations to calculate Euclidean distances to the ideal point. (ii) The second tier consists of NT_CD, which introduces a moderate computational overhead. While it shares the same NT mechanism for parent selection, its elitism strategy requires calculating PFs and crowding distances of the individuals in the first PF for the offspring population. Although more efficient than the full NSGA-II procedure, the necessity of performing the crowded comparison procedure

Table 2: Average computational time per fold in seconds (Mean \pm Std Dev).

	Algorithm	Boston	Cooling	Toxicity
2 Objectives	NSGA-II	1520.77 \pm 243.11	1776.43 \pm 680.71	1621.02 \pm 576.70
	NT_NSGA-II	1585.43 \pm 253.67	1564.98 \pm 175.92	2619.58 \pm 5052.52
	NT_1st_Obj	4.93 \pm 0.49	5.09 \pm 0.51	7.06 \pm 3.60
	NT_CD	478.99 \pm 117.29	440.26 \pm 39.16	599.31 \pm 204.66
	NT_Ideal_Cand	5.40 \pm 1.34	5.22 \pm 0.46	7.48 \pm 2.04
	NT_NE	5.09 \pm 0.95	5.08 \pm 0.50	7.28 \pm 1.97
3 Objectives	NSGA-II	2332.41 \pm 798.29	2529.04 \pm 815.13	2476.07 \pm 1886.36
	NT_NSGA-II	2248.47 \pm 396.33	2376.91 \pm 495.97	2507.82 \pm 1260.19
	NT_1st_Obj	6.69 \pm 0.79	6.92 \pm 0.80	9.18 \pm 5.04
	NT_CD	663.35 \pm 122.75	693.78 \pm 171.42	789.59 \pm 255.07
	NT_Ideal_Cand	6.93 \pm 1.16	7.16 \pm 1.14	9.41 \pm 2.44
	NT_NE	6.64 \pm 1.14	6.72 \pm 0.62	8.84 \pm 2.50
5 Objectives	NSGA-II	2993.47 \pm 460.02	4485.07 \pm 4044.42	4638.34 \pm 2262.26
	NT_NSGA-II	3449.37 \pm 625.20	5205.13 \pm 4131.91	5850.39 \pm 4863.73
	NT_1st_Obj	15.56 \pm 2.02	83.86 \pm 356.29	20.91 \pm 11.08
	NT_CD	1042.84 \pm 163.90	984.64 \pm 120.79	1270.53 \pm 411.18
	NT_Ideal_Cand	17.31 \pm 3.16	17.63 \pm 2.26	19.60 \pm 2.68
	NT_NE	16.36 \pm 2.18	16.46 \pm 1.81	19.22 \pm 3.91

for N individuals increases the per-generation cost. (iii) Finally, NSGA-II and NT_NSGA-II are consistently the slowest methods across all experiments. NSGA-II is hindered by the non-dominated sorting, which must merge and rank a combined population of $2N$ individuals in every generation. While NSGA-II and NT_NSGA-II often alternate in rank, NT_NSGA-II becomes consistently the most expensive variant in 5-objective scenarios. This computational cost arises because it combines the sequential overhead of multiple tournament layers during parent selection with the heavy $O(MN^2)$ sorting complexity of the NSGA-II replacement strategy.

4.2 Predictive Performance and Structural Complexity

RMSE was used to evaluate predictive performance and select the final model for each algorithm. Specifically, the individual with the lowest RMSE in the final generation was chosen, regardless of the elitism strategy. Structural complexity was assessed using tree size, a widely adopted proxy in the GP literature and included in all experiments, although additional complexity measures were considered in the 3- and 5-objective scenarios. The results shown and discussed below are integrated by supplementary Table SM-1, that reports the median and interquartile range (IQR) of RMSE and tree size for all datasets and multi-objective scenarios (2-, 3-, and 5-objective).

4.2.1 Boston Housing Dataset. Figure 2 presents boxplots of (A) training and test RMSE and (B) tree size distributions for the BH dataset under the 2-, 3-, and 5-objective scenarios. The p -values of the statistical tests for the BH dataset are provided in SM Tables 2, 4, and 6 for differences in test RMSE, and in SM Tables 3, 5, and 7 for differences in tree size.

The results show a clear and consistent trade-off between predictive performance (RMSE) and model complexity (tree size) across all experimental configurations. Across all objective scenarios, NSGA-II, NT_NSGA-II, and NT_1st_Obj achieve the lowest median RMSE, with all associated p -values ≤ 0.001 when compared to NT_CD,

Figure 2: (A) Training and test RMSE and (B) tree size distributions (30 runs) for the Boston dataset across all optimization objectives and evaluated algorithms.

NT_Ideal_Cand, and NT_NE. In the 2-objective scenario, although NSGA-II attains the lowest median error overall (6.54, vs. 7.15 for NT_NSGA-II and 7.22 for NT_1st_Obj, but with no statistically significant differences, p -values ≥ 0.151), it exhibits higher variability (IQR = 1.16, vs 0.97 for NT_NSGA-II and 0.85 for NT_1st_Obj), indicating less stable outcomes. As the number of objectives increases, both NSGA-II and NT_NSGA-II show modest degradation, with increases in RMSE and tree size, whereas NT_1st_Obj maintains a constant median tree size of 7 and achieves a slight RMSE reduction (median RMSE from 7.22 to 7.13 in the 2- to 5-objective transition) in the 5-objective setting.

In contrast, NT_CD, NT_Ideal_Cand, and NT_NE prioritise structural simplicity, producing consistently smaller models (median tree size = 3, with all associated p -values ≤ 0.001 for 2- and 3-objective scenarios, and for NT_CD in the 5-objective scenario in comparison to the best-performing models) but at the cost of higher RMSE. No statistically significant differences were observed among these lower-performing algorithms, with the exception of RMSE performance between NT_CD and NT_NE under the 3-objective configuration (median RMSE 9.35 vs. 10.25 with p -value = 0.036). While additional complexity-related objectives reduce their median RMSE without substantially increasing tree size, NT_NE in the 5-objective scenario exhibits an increase in tree size from 3 to 7, and NT_Ideal_Cand shows increased tree size variability (IQR from 0.00 to 4.00). This behavior is consistent with a weakened selective pressure toward complexity minimization in the absence of elitism under higher-dimensional objective settings.

Figure 3 shows the evolution of RMSE and tree size across generations for the BH dataset. The results indicate that NSGA-II, NT_NSGA-II, and NT_1st_Obj methods may benefit from an increased generational budget across objective configurations. For

Figure 3: Smoothed learning curves (10-generation interval) for the Boston dataset. (A) RMSE and (B) tree size, shown as medians with 15th-85th percentile bands over 30 runs.

NSGA-II and NT_1st_Obj, the stable gap between training and test curves also indicates that the search may still yield incremental improvements if extended. In contrast, NT_CD, NT_Ideal_Cand, and NT_NE remain trapped on an RMSE plateau, while tree size occasionally increases but is quickly reduced again, reflecting strong selection pressure towards structural simplicity. Across all variants, structural optimization appears easier than error reduction: tree size stabilises early, while RMSE decreases at a slower rate.

When considered alongside the computational time analysis, these findings highlight NT_1st_Obj as a particularly effective compromise between computational efficiency and predictive stability. Although it tends to produce slightly larger trees, its low RMSE and limited variability indicate a stable and well-controlled search behavior. These results suggest a promising direction for future work: by independently tuning selection pressure across objectives within the NT framework, it may be possible to relax parsimony constraints in a controlled manner, allowing moderate growth in structural complexity while further improving predictive performance.

4.2.2 Cooling Load Dataset. Figure 4 presents boxplots of (A) training and test RMSE and (B) tree size distributions for the CL dataset under the 2-, 3-, and 5-objective scenarios. The p -values of the statistical tests for the CL dataset are provided in SM Tables 8, 10, and 12 for differences in test RMSE, and in SM Tables 9, 11, and 13 for differences in tree size.

Compared to the BH dataset, the CL results show a less pronounced trade-off between RMSE and tree size. In the 2-objective scenario, NT_NE is significantly the worst performer in terms of RMSE (all p -values ≤ 0.001). In contrast, NSGA-II and NT_NSGA-II attain slightly lower errors (p -values ≤ 0.001 , except for p -value = 0.011 when compared to NT_1st_Obj). Considering the consistent small tree size of 3 of NT_Ideal_Cand and NT_CD, they provide a more favorable balance, combining competitive RMSE with smaller models. As the number of objectives increases, median RMSE generally rises across methods, specially for NT_Ideal_Cand

Figure 4: (A) Training and test RMSE and (B) tree size distributions (30 runs) for the Cooling dataset across all optimization objectives and evaluated algorithms.

and NT_CD. NSGA-II, NT_NSGA-II, and NT_1st_Obj partially offset this trend by simultaneously reducing median tree size, albeit at the cost of increased structural variability, in the case of NSGA-II and NT_NSGA-II. NT_CD maintains minimal model size in the 5-objective scenario but exhibits a sharp increase in RMSE variability (IQR = 0.23 in 2-objective scenario vs. IQR = 5.06 in 5-objective scenario), indicating unstable search behavior in high-dimensional objective spaces.

Figure 5 shows the evolution of RMSE and tree size across generations for CL dataset. The convergence behavior differs from that observed for BH, exhibiting a weaker overall learning trend. Although NSGA-II, NT_NSGA-II, and NT_1st_Obj reach competitive error levels, their learning curves in the 3- and 5-objective scenarios stagnate early, while tree size remains more constrained. This suggests that these methods likely reached a local optimum early in the process. Across all scenarios, strong pressure toward structural simplicity may be leading to lower size ceilings than in the BH experiments, constraining further reductions in error and resulting in flat RMSE trajectories.

The behavior of NT_CD, NT_Ideal_Cand, and NT_NE further reflects this pattern. While these variants occasionally start with lower RMSE values, they quickly shift toward solutions with higher errors, indicating that the selection pressure for structural parsimony dominated the search. The strict size constraints, evident in the learning curve plots, resulted in a reduction in predictive performance. As seen in the BH results, these observations further support the need for future research into adaptive selection pressure within the NT framework, to prevent premature emphasis on only one objective, in this case the structural simplicity.

For the 2-objective scenario, the NT_Ideal_Cand and NT_CD achieve superior predictive performance with small model size.

Figure 5: Smoothed learning curves (10-generation interval) for the Cooling dataset. (A) RMSE and (B) tree size, shown as medians with 15th-85th percentile bands over 30 runs.

For 3- and 5-objectives scenarios, NT_1st_Obj attains low median RMSE with smaller variability while maintaining a median tree size of 3, demonstrating a favourable balance of predictive performance and parsimony. Together with its computational efficiency, these results identify NT_1st_Obj as a particularly effective mechanism for generating compact MOGP models with consistently low RMSE, as observed for the BH dataset.

4.2.3 Toxicity Dataset. Figure 6 presents boxplots of (A) training and test RMSE and (B) tree size distributions for the LD50 dataset under the 2-, 3-, and 5-objective scenarios. The p -values of the statistical tests for the LD50 dataset are provided in SM Tables 14, 16, and 18 for differences in test RMSE, and in SM Tables 15, 17, and 19 for differences in tree size.

For the LD50 dataset in the 2- and 5-objective scenarios, NSGA-II, NT_NSGA-II, and NT_1st_Obj consistently achieve the lowest median RMSE (all associated p -values ≤ 0.003 in the 2-objective scenario, and ≤ 0.012 in the 5-objective scenario when compared to NT_CD, NT_Ideal_Cand, and NT_NE), consistent with the results observed for the BH dataset. In the 3-objective scenario, NT_NSGA-II and NT_1st_Obj emerge as the best performing methods in terms of RMSE, with no significant difference between them (p -value = 0.990). NSGA-II is not significantly different from the best-performing methods, but also not from the others, except from NT_NE. NT_Ideal_Cand and NT_CD present similar performance (p -value = 0.969), only with significant differences to the best-performing methods, except that NT_CD is not significantly different from NT_NE (p -value = 0.163). NT_NE performs worst, with significance differences in all other comparisons (p -values ≤ 0.019). NSGA-II exhibits weaker control over model complexity, producing both the largest median tree size (13 in all objective scenarios) and the highest structural variability (IQR of 8, 11, and 8 in 2-, 3-, and 5-objective scenarios).

Notably, the frequent occurrence of zero IQR values for tree size is most pronounced for the LD50 dataset, although it is also observed in several cases for the BH and CL datasets. This indicates that the search consistently converges to individuals of identical

Figure 6: (A) Training and test RMSE and (B) tree size distributions (30 runs) for the Toxicity dataset across all optimization objectives and evaluated algorithms.

small size, reflecting the relative ease of optimising structural complexity compared to predictive error. Although these solutions share similar structural complexity, differing RMSE values confirm that they correspond to distinct individuals. This pattern suggests that, under strong parsimony pressure, maximum tree depth becomes effectively irrelevant and may therefore be omitted as a hyperparameter in MOGP parsimony search.

Figure 7 shows the evolution of RMSE and tree size across generations for LD50 dataset. The RMSE lower bound was adjusted to improve visual comparison. Across all objective configurations, NSGA-II allows substantially larger tree sizes from the earliest generations, without corresponding gains in predictive performance. In the 2- and 3-objective scenarios, NT_NSGA-II and NT_1st_Obj exhibit a sustained downward trend in RMSE, indicating incomplete convergence and a potential benefit from a larger generational budget, as observed for BH results. In contrast, NT_CD, NT_Ideal_Cand, and NT_NE stagnate in the 2- and 5-objective scenarios, with NT_NE also stagnating in the 3-objective case, a behavior consistent with premature convergence under strong parsimony-driven selection pressure. Across all objective scenarios, NT_NSGA-II and NT_1st_Obj achieve competitive RMSE with smaller tree sizes. NSGA-II produces the largest tree sizes, without corresponding gains in predictive performance. As observed in BH and CL datasets, NT_1st_Obj therefore emerges as the most efficient variant when combined with shorter running times.

4.3 Fitness Diversity Analysis

Figure 8 shows the evolution of fitness diversity, measured as the standard deviation of RMSE within the population, across generations for the BH, CL, and LD50 datasets. The y-axis is shown on a

Figure 7: Smoothed learning curves (10-generation interval) for the Toxicity dataset. (A) RMSE and (B) tree size, shown as medians with 15th-85th percentile bands over 30 runs.

logarithmic scale to accommodate the large differences in magnitude observed across methods. Although this scaling reduces visual discrimination among NT_1st_Obj, NT_CD, NT_Ideal_Cand, and NT_NE, it clearly exposes the distinct dynamics of the NSGA-II-based algorithms. Across all datasets, NSGA-II and NT_NSGA-II

Figure 8: RMSE population standard deviation evolution across generations for Boston, Cooling and Toxicity datasets, shown as medians with 15th-85th percentile bands over 30 runs for all evaluated scenarios.

exhibit the poorest preservation of fitness error diversity. In all cases, the RMSE standard deviation collapses within the first generations and stabilises at very low levels, indicating an early loss of predictive diversity. This contrasts with the remaining variants, for which fitness diversity remains substantially higher throughout the search. This behavior is counterintuitive given the use of crowding distance in NSGA-II algorithm, but the observed dynamics indicate that crowding distance is ineffective in this setting for generating less complex models. As structural complexity dominates selection pressure, the low variability in tree size prevents crowding distance from discriminating sparsity in the objective space, thereby weakening its ability to preserve fitness diversity. Overall, these results show that under strong parsimony pressure, NSGA-II-based elitism induces an early collapse of fitness error diversity, revealing a fundamental limitation of crowding distance in asymmetric MOGP landscapes.

Overall, NSGA-II, NT_NSGA-II, and NT_1st_Obj achieve the best trade-offs between predictive performance and solution complexity. Owing to its orders-of-magnitude computational advantage and superior diversity preservation, NT_1st_Obj emerges as particularly efficient for generating compact MOGP models. Preserving a single RMSE elite is sufficient in this problem, likely because RMSE dominates the selection dynamics as the most difficult objective. In problems with different dominance structures, one elite per objective may be required. More generally, these results show that effective elitism in NT does not require explicit PF construction and position NT as a promising general framework for MOGP.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This work presented the first systematic analysis of elitism strategies within the Nested Tournament (NT) selection framework for generating less complex Multi-Objective Genetic Programming (MOGP) models. By comparing Pareto-Front-based, objective-driven, and non-elitist mechanisms under increasing objective dimensionality, we showed that elitism design critically determines stability, diversity preservation, and computational efficiency within the NT framework. Integrating NSGA-II population replacement into NT provides a principled elitist mechanism but incurs substantial computational overhead and degrades in many-objective settings. Under strong parsimony pressure, NSGA-II-based elitism consistently induces early collapse of fitness error diversity, revealing a limitation of crowding distance when the selection dynamics among the objectives is asymmetric. In contrast, simpler objective-driven elitism strategies achieve comparable error vs. complexity trade-offs at orders-of-magnitude lower cost while maintaining more stable evolutionary dynamics and higher fitness diversity. Overall, NT selection emerges as a competitive and efficient alternative to Pareto-Front-based MOGP, provided that elitism is explicitly and appropriately designed. Future work will investigate adaptive NT configurations, including dynamic tournament sizing, objective ordering, and diversity-aware elitism mechanisms.

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